

EFFECT OF ORGANIC POTATO (SOLANUM TUBEROSUM L.) CULTIVATION TECHNOLOGY ON PRODUCT MEDICINAL PROPERTIES

Effect of organic potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) cultivation technology on
product medicinal properties

Samarkand State University named of Sharof Rashidov

Institute of Agrobiotechnologies and Food Safety

Student: Azzamov Khamrokhan son of Aktamkhan

hamroxonazzamov582@gmail.com

Abstract. This article discusses the impact of organic potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) cultivation technology on medicinal properties of the product in the developing agricultural sector.

On the basis of advanced technologies in agriculture, different amounts of organic fertilizers (from 0 to 40 t/ha) were applied to mid-early "SANTE" potatoes in the grassy gray soils of DJambay district, Samarkand region. divided into four different options and conducted an experiment based on one return. Phenological and biometric parameters of the control variant and the remaining three variants were monitored during the vegetation period. According to the results of the experiment, it was found that the medicinal properties of the obtained product increased by 22-30% compared to the control variant.

Key words: *Solanum tuberosum* L, grassland gray soils, mid-early ripening "SANTE" variety, organic fertilizers, phenological, biometric, medicinal composition.

Introduction

Potato (Latin: *Solanum tuberosum* L.) is a perennial herbaceous plant

with nodular fruits belonging to the Solanaceae family; One of the main food products is cultivated for the purposes of obtaining food, machinery, medicinal products and for processing feed in livestock. Homeland - South America. About 150 wild and cultivated species grow mostly in South and Central America. It has been cultivated in America for 1400 thousand years. It was brought to Europe in 1565. It was cultivated in Russia at the beginning of the 18th century. It was brought to Uzbekistan by Russians and Tatars who immigrated to Uzbekistan in the 70s of the 19th century.

It occupies the second place after wheat, corn and rice in terms of the cultivated area of the earth, and in terms of importance, it takes the second place after wheat.

As of 2022, a total of 11,167 hectares of cultivated areas were planted with high-quality and high-yielding varieties of potatoes, and a harvest of 39,461 tons was achieved.

Potato is a universal crop that can be used as food, fodder, technical and medicinal products. Tuber biochemical composition: 75% water and 25% dry matter, 70-80% of the dry matter is starch, its content is 13-20%, protein-2-3%, fiber-1%, oil-0.2-0.3%, sugar-1%, ash- It contains 0.8-1% and a large amount of potassium (568mg per 100g. raw tuber), phosphorus (50mg), calcium and iron.

Potato tubers contain various vitamins (in g per 100 g raw mass) PP-0.04-2.0, B1-0.05-0.12, B2-0.01, B6-0.08-0.22, P-1.3, pantothenic acid -0.2-0.3, carotene (provitamin A) -0.05 and a small amount of vitamins K, I, D, E. The content of vitamin C in tuber is 10-30 mg, and in some circumstances it can reach 50 mg. The amount of vitamin C is especially high in immature young buds.

Due to the high content of potassium, potatoes remove excess salt and water from the body, which improves metabolism. That's why potatoes are very useful during a diet, but one should not forget about moderation. Because it is a high-calorie product, it is recommended to consume less for people prone to obesity.

Drinking potato juice together with carrot and celery root juice improves digestion and relieves nervous tension.

If you have heart problems, if you eat 100 ml of potato juice three times a day on an empty stomach (for three weeks), then take a break for 1 week and repeat this course of treatment, you will get rid of this disease.

Even the strongest fungal diseases can be overcome by drinking thick potato decoction every day.

It should be noted that potatoes that have come out on the surface of the soil or turned blue during storage can lead to severe poisoning due to the high concentration of the toxic substance solanine.

As a result of our experiment, it was found that the amount of organic food, which is the only factor of the experiment, which affects the amount of useful compounds contained in the "SANTE" variety of potato, has an effective effect on the medicinal content of the crop obtained from different variants.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was carried out in the grassy gray soils of Djambay district, Samarkand region. First, the F1 generation of the potato variety was selected for seed, the storage location was selected, the experimental planting area was selected, and the amount of organic fertilizer in the soil was determined.

At the experimental site, agrotechnical measures were carried out at a qualitative level, and organic feed standards were distributed according to the options. Observation work was carried out in the experimental plot divided into four types (1-control (without fertilizer), 2- 25t/ha, 3-30t/ha, 4-40t/ha).

RESULTS OBTAINED AND THEIR ANALYSIS

Observation work was carried out in four variants of the experiment carried out on the "SANTE" potato variety at the experimental plot of organic potato

cultivation technology. As a result of observations, the selected seeds germinated in 25-30 days at a temperature of 18-22°C, the length of the plant stem was 30-40 cm during the flowering period. Vegetation period was 85 days in total.

It was found that the distribution of organic fertilizers in the section of options compared to the control option (without fertilizer) increased by 15-20% in terms of productivity and increased by 22-30% in terms of medicinal (biochemical) content of the product.

CONCLUSION

In the experimental process of growing organic potatoes, 25 to 40 tons of well-rotted organic fertilizers, the same amount of irrigation, and agrotechnical work of soil softening were applied to the experimental plot according to the options (except for the control option) twice (30 and 45 days of the vegetation period days) was carried out.

We have implemented the most effective methods of combating the pests of potatoes, the Colorado potato beetle, the potato moth, whitefly, and weeds, as well as the prevention of the most harmful diseases of the plant - "rhizoctoniosis" and "fusariosis".

In order to harvest the crop in good quality, we cleaned the furrows and weeds from potatoes 5-6 days before digging.

As a result of the timely implementation of all the above-mentioned agrotechnical measures, an abundant harvest with high biochemical content was harvested.

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